

THE STUDY OF THE EASTERN PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN POLICY AND KNOWLEDGE

Keywords: European Union, Eastern Partnership, policy, knowledge, study.

Introduction.

In 2019 the Eastern Partnership initiative got to the anniversary of ten years. During this period the Eastern Partnership has become an overused concept both in the European Union and in the countries covered by the initiative. The Eastern Partnership is a topic that fills the agenda each year, but still remains problematic in the framework of cooperation. Reasoning on this aspect, the paper focuses on the relation between the Eastern Partnership policy and knowledge on the Eastern Partnership. The study of the Eastern Partnership is not an ordinary exercise; it needs a complex approach in dealing properly it, especially research and collection of empirical data on the Eastern Partnership, which seems to be neglected a bit by involved actors.

Policy.

The Eastern Partnership initiative is a part of the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP). The Eastern Partnership (EaP) is a joint policy initiative, launched by Poland and Sweden in 2009, with the scope to deepen and strengthen relations between the European Union, its Member States and six neighbours in Eastern Europe (Belarus, Moldova, Ukraine) and South Caucasus (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia).

Cooperation in the Eastern Partnership comprises bilateral and multilateral tracks. The history of cooperation is full of multiple actions and measures. The milestones could be summarised compactly: launch of the new Eastern Partnership cooperation set-up (2018); annual meeting of the Conference of Regional and Local Authorities for the Eastern Partnership (CORLEAP), Eastern Partnership Media Conference in Kyiv, Eastern Partnership E-partnership Conference in Tallinn, Eastern Partnership Civil Society Conference in Tallinn, Eastern Partnership Business Forum in Tallinn, EaP Summit in Brussels (2017); DCFTA between Ukraine and the EU becomes operational (2016); ENP progress reports on 5 Eastern neighbours, EaP Summit in Riga, beginning of the provisional application of DCFTA between the EU and Georgia, some provisions of AA/DCFTA between the EU and Moldova enter into force, European Commission presents a review of European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) (2015); Ukraine signs political part of Association Agreement, ENP progress reports on 5 Eastern neighbours, citizens of Moldova start travelling visa-free to Europe, Georgia and Moldova sign Association Agreements, Ukraine signs Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) provisions of Association Agreement, the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) comes into force with a budget of €15.4 billion for the period 2014-2020 replacing the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI) (2014); ENP progress reports on 5 Eastern neighbours, Eastern Partnership (EaP) in Vilnius: Moldova and Georgia initial

Association Agreements with the EU, Ukraine defers initialling (2013); ENP progress reports on 5 Eastern neighbours, Council sets priorities of cooperation with South Caucasus (2012); Eastern Partnership Summit in Warsaw, launch of the Conference of Regional and Local Authorities for the Eastern Partnership (CORLEAP), EURONEST Parliamentary Assembly launched, ENP progress reports on 5 Eastern neighbours, launch of renewed European Neighbourhood Policy (2011); EU strengthens European Neighbourhood Policy with €5.7 billion for 2011-2013 (2010); Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum launched, Eastern Partnership launched during Summit in Prague (2009).

The launch of the new Eastern Partnership cooperation set-up (2018) follows to be more result-oriented, more systematic and more visible [4]. The new set-up includes agreed priorities and results in the Eastern Partnership – 20 Deliverables for 2020 Focusing on Key Priorities and Tangible Results (2017): *cross-cutting deliverables* – (1) structured engagement with civil society, (2) gender equality and non-discrimination, (3) strategic communication and plurality and independence of media; *economic development and market opportunities* – (4) regulatory environment and SMEs development, (5) gaps in access to finance and financial infrastructure, (6) new job opportunities at local and regional level, (7) harmonisation of digital markets, (8) trade and DCFTA implementation; *strengthening institutions and good governance* – (9) rule of law and anti-corruption mechanisms, (10) implementation of key judicial reforms, (11) implementation of public administration reform, (12) security; *connectivity, energy efficiency, environment and climate change* – (13) extension of the TEN-T core networks, (14) energy supply, (15) energy efficiency, renewable energy and reduction of Greenhouse gas emissions, (16) environment and adaptation to climate change; *mobility and people-to-people contacts* – (17) visa liberalisation and mobility partnerships, (18) youth, education, skills development and culture, (19) Eastern Partnership European School, (20) research and innovation [3].

Study and Knowledge.

Policy references show that there are fissures in the relation to the Eastern Partnership. But still “the Eastern Partnership is crucial for the EU and the West” [6]. Jan Techau (2013) underlines that the “EU’s approach toward its Eastern neighbors matters hugely for the region, for the EU, and for the West as a whole. That approach needs to be bolder and more strategic” [6]. Steven Blockmans (2019) considers that the “EU’s Eastern Partnership programme is often underestimated for what it has accomplished but overestimated for what it can achieve” [2]. On the one hand, there is recognition of the importance of the Eastern Partnership as such. On the other hand, there is also recognition of problematic Eastern Partnership.

The applied approach to the Eastern Partnership is in line with the principles of differentiation, strict conditionality, joint ownership, joint responsibility and solidarity, “more for more” and “less for less”. However, there is a critical omission, insufficient knowledge/research/study of the Eastern Partnership. The Eastern Partnership policy includes geography of countries with different histories, cultures, traditions, religions. What unites all Eastern Partnership countries is that they once belonged to the defunct Soviet Union. Thus, the Eastern Partnership means a lot of ambiguity that is perceivable, visible and ‘tangible’.

Steven Blockmans (2014) identifies seven key structural challenges to the Eastern Partnership: (1) How can the EaP take account of the ties between the EaP countries and Russia and the interests of Moscow?; (2) The EaP is designed for long-term effects but is not useful for the short-term crisis management. How should it deal with the lack of a hard security dimension?; (3) How to ensure proper implementation of the DCFTA?; (4) How to improve the merit-based approach for frontrunners?; (5) Maintaining unity within diversity; (6) Managing asymmetric expectations; (7) Overcoming splits among EU Member States on how to strengthen the EaP [1].

These academic interrogations lead to the idea of vacuum of knowledge on the Eastern Partnership. More research is needed for the study of the Eastern Partnership. An inventory of knowledge/empirical data on the Eastern Partnership seems to be one of the major challenges for all actors: the European Union, its Member States and all six Eastern Partnership countries themselves. Aspirations and exhortations are to be based on evaluation, cemented on extended research and study of the problems the Eastern Partnership countries face individually and collectively otherwise a difficult future is ensured.

Recommendations

A pertinent point of view is expressed by Tamas Novak about the future of the Eastern Partnership, which is seen between strategic changes and continued drifting. The author admits three possible options: EU membership of the countries concerned, *maintaining buffer zones between the EU and Russia or drifting without declaring the final objective* [5]. Additionally, he makes policy recommendations on problematic Eastern Partnership: "(1) Make a clear decision about the objective of the Eastern Partnership and make it an integral part of a consistent EU foreign policy. If the EU aims at becoming a credible and serious actor in international affairs, it must become a power which is able to resolve complicated regional conflicts. (2) Consider value based policy-making more important than simple 'realpolitik' – even if it requires more effort. (3) Create undivided member state support behind the policy and explain to every stakeholder – most importantly EU citizens and Eastern Partnership leaders and the people – the reasons behind choosing the accepted alternative over other available options" [5].

Certainly these policy recommendations require proper evaluation exercise and research findings to be functional and efficient. Joint EU-EaP research teams would bring added value by involving all parties concerned by the policy.

Conclusions.

The Eastern Partnership region requires being studied better, i.e. performing research and providing of teaching both in the European Union and the Eastern Partnership countries.

Collection of empirical data on the Eastern Partnership using them in policy (ies) shaping and cooperation development between the European Union and the Eastern Partnership countries are also encouraged.

For better effectiveness of the Eastern Partnership (EaP) initiative of the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) it is needed to diversify cooperation between the actors by exploiting vertical, horizontal and transversal dimensions.

References:

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